

Received: 20.4.2026.

Accepted: 12.5.2026.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.21127967

Original Scientific Article

Originalni naučni članak

PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY: BETWEEN EXPECTATIONS AND REALITY

Katarina Tomic¹

Academy of Applied Preschool Teaching and Health Studies Krusevac, Republic of Serbia

Abstract

Contemporary society places increasingly complex demands on preschool teachers, extending beyond the traditional boundaries of their professional role. They are expected to act simultaneously as educators, psychologists, innovators, digitally competent professionals, and active collaborators within the community. In this context, the professional identity of preschool teachers is shaped at the intersection of institutional expectations, social norms, and personal values, often creating tension between idealized roles and the realities of everyday practice. The aim of this paper is to analyze the key dimensions of preschool teachers' professional identity within the contemporary educational system, with particular emphasis on challenges arising from rapid social change, digitalization, and evolving expectations of parents and institutions. The paper draws on contemporary theoretical approaches to professional identity, as well as empirical insights into perceptions of the preschool teacher's role. Special attention is given to the discrepancy between the normative framework of the profession and everyday practice, as well as to the strategies that preschool teachers develop to preserve professional autonomy and integrity. The paper also highlights the importance of continuous professional development, reflective practice, and systemic support in building a stable and coherent professional identity. In conclusion, the paper points to the need for redefining social and institutional expectations in order to align the professional identity of preschool teachers with the real conditions and needs of contemporary education, thereby improving both the quality of educational practice and the professional status of preschool teachers in society.

Keywords: professional identity, preschool teachers, contemporary society, professional development, reflective practice

¹ katarinat@vaspks.edu.rs

Introduction

The issue of preschool teachers' professional identity has increasingly come into focus in contemporary discussions on preschool upbringing and education in recent years. Numerous social and educational changes, curriculum reforms, as well as evolving expectations regarding preschool institutions and educators themselves, have contributed to the fact that the professional role of preschool teachers is now viewed in a significantly broader and more complex way than before. They are no longer expected merely to implement predefined activities, but rather to demonstrate the capacity for reflective thinking, collaboration, continuous learning, and active participation in the development of educational practice.

In such circumstances, professional identity cannot be regarded as something fixed and unchangeable. On the contrary, it develops and evolves throughout professional experience, under the influence of personal beliefs, relationships with colleagues and children, the institutional environment, as well as broader social and educational changes. The way preschool teachers understand their profession, their own competencies, and their responsibilities is shaped through everyday practice and the continuous alignment between personal professional values and the demands set by the contemporary educational system.

Contemporary research on professional identity indicates that preschool teachers' identity develops through a process of continuous re-examination of professional beliefs, professional experience, and attitudes toward one's own practice. Androusou and Tsafos (2018) emphasize that the professional identity of educators emerges through interconnected processes of initial education, professional integration, and continuous professional development. The authors stress that professional identity is not only the result of formal education, but also a product of dominant professional discourses and social representations of the teaching profession. In this sense, professional identity represents both a personal and a social construction that develops and changes throughout professional life.

In contemporary society, the profession of preschool teachers faces numerous challenges, as they are expected to be reflective practitioners, researchers of their own practice, creators of stimulating learning environments, partners to families, and active participants in the development of learning communities. At the same time, the profession is confronted with issues of insufficient social recognition, administrative burden, and ongoing reform demands. Precisely for this reason, the question of professional identity has become crucial for understanding the contemporary role of early childhood educators.

On Professional Identity

The professional identity of early childhood educators in contemporary theoretical approaches is viewed as a complex, dynamic, and continuously evolving construct shaped through the interaction between an individual's personal characteristics and the broader social, institutional, and professional context. Professional identity is not a static category but a process of continuous development, questioning, and reconstruction throughout one's professional career (Beijaard et al., 2004).

In the literature, professional identity is often described as a dynamic mosaic of various individual, social, and professional factors, whose meanings and interrelationships change throughout an individual's professional path (Akkerman & Meijer, 2011). This understanding emphasizes that educators simultaneously integrate their own professional beliefs with the norms, values, and practices that dominate within the professional community. Professional identity thus

develops through the alignment of personal professional aspirations with what is considered desirable and competent professional practice within a given social and institutional context. In this sense, professional identity is simultaneously an individual, social, and institutional phenomenon, as it emerges at the intersection of an individual's psychological structures and the social structures within which they operate (Trede et al., 2012). Its construction involves an active process of reflection on one's own role, professional competencies, responsibilities, and relationships with children, families, colleagues, and the wider community. For this reason, the professional identity of preschool teachers cannot be viewed in isolation from the context in which professional practice takes place, particularly in the context of contemporary educational reforms and curriculum changes.

In the field of early childhood education and care, the professional identity of educators gains additional complexity due to shifts in the understanding of the child, learning, and the educator's role within the contemporary curriculum. The educator is positioned as an active facilitator of learning and a partner in a learning community, which significantly contributes to the redefinition of professional roles and professional identity (Hanhikoski & Sevón, 2024). In this regard, professional identity represents an important factor in professional development, the quality of educational practice, and educators' readiness to embrace innovation and change in education. While professional identity refers to how individuals understand and define themselves within their profession, it is closely related to their *personal professional paradigm*, which reflects the beliefs, values, and assumptions that guide their professional thinking and practice.

Personal Professional Paradigm

The personal professional paradigm of preschool teachers represents a complex system of implicit and explicit beliefs, values, attitudes, experiences, and professional knowledge that shape the way they understand their own professional role. In the literature, this concept is often associated with *implicit pedagogies*, that is, with a set of personal theories and assumptions that individuals develop through their own education, professional experience, and socialization (Salamon et al., 2016). These implicit theories are most often not fully conscious, yet they significantly influence everyday professional practice and pedagogical decision-making.

The personal professional paradigm can be understood as a kind of "internal compass" that guides educators in interpreting situations, selecting teaching methods, organizing learning environments, and establishing relationships with children, families, and colleagues. It determines how educators perceive the child—whether as a passive recipient of knowledge or as an active participant and competent being—as well as how they understand learning processes, discipline, collaboration, and child development. For this reason, the same educational policy or curriculum may be interpreted and implemented differently in practice, depending on the practitioner's personal professional paradigm.

Contemporary theoretical approaches indicate that the personal professional paradigm has a multi-layered structure. Its deepest layers consist of fundamental life and professional beliefs, value orientations, and attitudes about children, learning, and society. On a more surface level are concrete pedagogical strategies, behavioral patterns, and everyday professional decisions that emerge from these deeper beliefs (Korthagen, 2004). For this reason, changes in practice cannot be achieved solely through external reforms and administrative requirements but require a process of internal professional transformation and reflection.

The development of a personal professional paradigm is influenced by numerous factors: early childhood and schooling experiences, initial professional education, practical experience, institutional culture, collaboration with colleagues, professional development activities, as well as

dominant social and cultural discourses about children and education. Reflective practice and professional dialogue play a particularly important role, as they enable educators to examine their implicit beliefs and align them with contemporary pedagogical approaches (Hanhikoski & Sevón, 2024). Professional development, therefore, does not only involve acquiring new competencies and knowledge, but also changing the way one thinks about one's own practice.

In contemporary early childhood education, the need for critical examination of the personal professional paradigm becomes especially pronounced in the context of curriculum reforms and shifts in understandings of children and learning. New curricula, based on child participation, collaborative learning, and reflective practice, require educators to move away from traditional transmissive models of teaching and to develop a more flexible and open professional approach. Consequently, increasing emphasis is placed on the development of the reflective practitioner who continuously analyzes, questions, and transforms their own professional beliefs and practice (Korthagen, 2004; Salamon et al., 2016).

Thus, the personal professional paradigm represents an important foundation of educators' professional identity and directly influences the quality of educational practice. Its awareness and development contribute to greater professional autonomy, readiness for innovation, and a more effective response to the needs of children and contemporary society.

Higher Education Reforms and the Professionalization of the Early Childhood Educator Profession

Reforms of initial preschool teachers' education in the Republic of Serbia are part of broader changes in the higher education system that followed the country's inclusion in the Bologna Process at the beginning of the 21st century. The aim of these reforms was to align the national education system with European standards, improve the quality of study programs, increase student mobility, and strengthen the professional competencies of future educators. In this context, significant changes occurred in the organization, structure, and conceptualization of early childhood educator education.

The traditional model of educator education in Serbia was long based on colleges and pedagogical academies, which primarily prepared personnel for practical work in preschool institutions. However, with the adoption of the Bologna Process principles, these institutions began to transform into colleges of applied studies and later into academies of applied studies, thereby giving initial educator education a new institutional and organizational framework. These changes included the introduction of the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), modular structuring of curricula, the redefinition of learning outcomes, and a stronger focus on the development of professional competencies (Zakon o visokom obrazovanju, 2025).

The Bologna Process has also brought significant changes in the understanding of the professional role of early childhood educators. Instead of the traditional model in which preschool teachers were primarily seen as implementers of predefined programs, contemporary approaches emphasize the need to educate reflective practitioners capable of critically examining their own practice, conducting inquiry into their work, and actively participating in curriculum development (Stanković et al., 2019). Modern curricular approaches require educators to develop competencies for collaboration, documentation of learning processes, teamwork, and continuous professional development, which has also influenced the redefinition of the content of initial education.

However, despite these reform efforts, numerous studies indicate a gap between the theoretical content delivered during studies and the actual demands of professional practice. Educators often report that initial education does not provide sufficient concrete experience and

practical competencies for work in contemporary preschool contexts, particularly in the areas of inclusive education, cooperation with families, and the implementation of modern curricular approaches (Stamenković, 2025). A particular challenge lies in the insufficient connection between theoretical knowledge and authentic practice situations, which often leads to uncertainty among novice professionals when entering the field.

One of the most significant challenges of the reform concerns the preparedness of educators to work in diverse and inclusive environments. Research shows that many students acquire mainly declarative knowledge about inclusion during their initial education, while lacking practical strategies for individualization, cooperation with support professionals, and working with children with diverse developmental and educational needs (Mihic, 2017). The contemporary concept of inclusive education requires educators to demonstrate flexibility, reflexivity, and the ability to adapt to diverse children's needs, which goes beyond traditional understandings of the professional role.

The transformation of colleges of applied studies into academies of applied studies represents another important step in the reform of higher education in Serbia. These changes aim to strengthen the academic status of vocational education, improve the quality of study programs, and better connect theory, research, and professional practice. At the same time, these reforms raise the question of preserving the specific nature of the preschool teacher profession and the need to establish a balance between academic theory and the practical competencies required for work in contemporary preschool contexts.

Professionalization Processes in Early Childhood Education

The process of professionalizing the preschool teacher profession in Serbia is closely linked to reforms in higher education and changes in the conceptualization of early childhood education. With the introduction of the Bologna Process and the transformation of colleges into higher education institutions of an academic type, the profession has gained a more pronounced scientific, research, and reflective dimension. This has also changed the traditional understanding of the profession, which had long been primarily focused on the practical and caregiving aspects of working with children. In this context, the importance of horizontal exchange and professional learning communities is particularly emphasized as key supports for professional development. Korać and Djermanov (2023) define horizontal learning as a process of co-construction of knowledge among equal participants, based on reflective dialogue, critical questioning, and the examination of theory and practice from multiple perspectives. Such an approach to professional development contributes to the transformation of professional identity, as educators are no longer passive recipients of expert knowledge, but active participants in its co-creation and reinterpretation.

The particular significance of horizontal learning is reflected in the development of professional learning communities characterized by mutual trust, collaboration, shared values, and a readiness to change practice. In this way, the professional identity of educators becomes closely linked to continuous learning, collaboration, and professional reflection. Professional development is thus no longer viewed as an individual process of acquiring new knowledge, but rather as a collective process of co-constructing professional knowledge and the professional culture of an institution (Pavlović-Breneselović & Krnjaja, 2012).

However, research shows that, despite the recognized importance of horizontal learning, its implementation in practice still faces numerous obstacles. Insufficient institutional support, administrative overload, lack of time, and an unfavorable organizational climate often hinder the development of a culture of collaboration and reflective practice. This further affects the

professional identity of educators, which is often positioned between contemporary professional expectations and the constraints of the real institutional context.

“Years of Ascent” and the Transformation of Preschool Teachers’ Professional Identity

One of the most significant factors contributing to the redefinition of preschool teachers’ professional identity in Serbia is the new Preschool Education Curriculum Framework “Years of Ascent”. This policy document introduces not only changes in the organization and planning of educational work, but also a transformation in the very philosophy of early childhood education.

The “Years of Ascent” concept is based on the understanding of the child as a competent and active participant in their own development and learning. At the core of the program are the child’s well-being, participation, relationships, community, exploration, and play. Such an approach also transforms the traditional role of the educator. The educator is no longer seen as an implementer of predefined content and activities, but rather as a partner to the child and a co-constructor of the curriculum, who jointly explores, documents, and develops the educational program with children (Pravilnik o osnovama programa predškolskog vaspitanja i obrazovanja, 2018).

This paradigm shift requires a corresponding transformation of educators’ professional identity, as they are expected to demonstrate a higher degree of professional autonomy, flexibility, and an inquiry-based approach. In this context, professional identity develops through everyday joint reflection on practice, collaboration with colleagues and families, and active participation in learning communities.

Krnjaja (2016, pp. 16–18) emphasizes that the quality of early childhood education should not be understood as a set of predefined standards, but rather as a process of co-constructing meaning within a specific community of practice. The author defines quality as a multi-perspective, context-dependent, and value-laden concept that develops through collaboration, reflection, and participation of all actors in the educational process. Such an understanding of quality directly influences educators’ professional identity, as it requires active professional responsibility, collaborative competence, and continuous professional self-reflection.

Within the “Years of Ascent” framework, the institutional culture as a learning community gains particular importance. Professional identity is not formed in isolation but through relationships with colleagues, children, families, and the wider social community. For this reason, contemporary approaches to early childhood education emphasize the importance of collaborative inquiry and professional dialogue. However, the process of transforming professional identity is not straightforward. Curriculum changes often generate a sense of professional uncertainty among educators, especially when there is insufficient systemic support for understanding and implementing new program concepts. In addition, the mismatch between contemporary professional expectations and traditional societal perceptions of the profession further complicates the process of professional transformation.

Status of the Preschool Teacher Profession in Contemporary Society

The status of the preschool teacher profession in contemporary society represents an important issue within the field of preschool education, particularly in the context of increasingly high expectations placed upon this profession. Although contemporary curricula and education policies emphasize the crucial role of early education for the development of the child and society

as a whole, research shows that the social status of early childhood educators in Serbia remains relatively low and insufficiently recognized in relation to the complexity and significance of their professional role (Miljković, 2011).

Preschool teachers generally perceive their professional work as highly responsible, emotionally demanding, and complex, as it involves simultaneously providing care for children, planning and implementing educational activities, collaborating with families, documenting learning processes, and engaging in continuous professional development. However, despite the complexity of these professional tasks, there is still a prevailing social perception of educators as “babysitters,” that is, individuals whose primary role is childcare rather than pedagogically grounded professional work (Banković, 2014). Such perceptions contribute to the devaluation of the profession and insufficient recognition of educators’ professional competencies. The inadequate social perception of the profession is therefore linked to historically rooted understandings of early childhood education as primarily a caring rather than an educational activity. Although contemporary approaches emphasize the educational, developmental, and social functions of preschool institutions, social perceptions often lag behind changes in theory and practice. Consequently, educators frequently feel that their professional contribution is not sufficiently visible, valued, or socially acknowledged.

In addition to issues of social perception, preschool teachers also frequently point to a sense of marginalization in decision-making processes related to the preschool education system. Research indicates that practitioners often feel they bear significant responsibility for the quality of practice and the implementation of reforms, while simultaneously having limited influence on the development of educational policies and professional standards (Kizevski & Radović, 2023). Such a position can contribute to a sense of professional powerlessness and reduced professional autonomy, which is also reflected in educators’ professional identity.

The status of the profession is also influenced by broader social and economic factors. The early childhood educator profession traditionally belongs to highly feminized occupations, which in sociological analyses is often associated with lower social prestige and weaker financial valuation of work. The predominantly female composition of the profession, combined with relatively low salaries and limited opportunities for career advancement, contributes to the perception of the profession as less socially prestigious (Jurčević Lozančić, 2023). Furthermore, some authors note that long-term insufficient investment in the profession may also lead to negative selection of personnel, i.e., reduced interest among highly motivated candidates in choosing this profession.

Contemporary reform processes further complicate the professional position of preschool teachers. They are expected to develop new competencies, demonstrate readiness for continuous professional development, engage in reflective practice, and actively participate in curriculum development, while social recognition and institutional support often do not match these professional demands. Therefore, contemporary literature increasingly emphasizes the need to strengthen professional autonomy, improve working conditions, and enhance educators’ participation in the educational decision-making process, in order to improve both the social status and professional identity of this profession.

Challenges and Problems of the Preschool Teacher Profession

The contemporary context of early childhood education presents numerous challenges that affect educators’ professional identity, autonomy, and the quality of their work. Although reform processes emphasize the importance of professionalization and the improvement of preschool education quality, everyday practice shows that educators often face various structural,

organizational, and interpersonal obstacles that hinder the implementation of contemporary pedagogical principles.

One of the most frequently highlighted issues concerns the administrative burden placed on educators. In modern early childhood education systems, increasing importance is given to documenting learning processes, maintaining pedagogical records, developing portfolios, and various forms of evaluation. Although the primary purpose of documentation is to enhance reflective practice and monitor child development, educators often perceive it as an excessive administrative obligation that reduces the time and energy available for direct work with children (Kizevski & Radović, 2023). When documentation becomes formalized and primarily oriented toward meeting administrative requirements, there is a risk that it loses its developmental and reflective function.

In addition to administrative demands, significant challenges also arise from structural problems within preschool institutions. Large group sizes, lack of space, insufficient material resources, and limited professional support make it difficult to implement contemporary curricular approaches based on individualization, child participation, and exploratory learning. In such conditions, educators are often unable to fully respond to individual children's needs or to implement activities in accordance with modern pedagogical principles. These conditions may contribute to professional dissatisfaction, feelings of exhaustion, and reduced motivation for professional development.

A particular challenge also concerns the relationship between educators' professional autonomy and various forms of external control and evaluation. Contemporary quality assurance systems involve external evaluation of institutional work and monitoring of educational standards, which can in certain cases contribute to the improvement of practice. However, research shows that educators often experience external evaluation as a form of pressure toward standardization and formal control, which may limit creativity and autonomy in their work (Kizevski & Radović, 2023). When the focus shifts toward compliance with procedures and external requirements, there is a risk that professional practice becomes reduced to formal fulfillment of criteria rather than the authentic development of educational quality.

Interpersonal relationships within educational teams also significantly influence preschool teachers' professional satisfaction and development. Contemporary reforms emphasize a culture of collaboration and teamwork; however, practice shows that resistance to change, insufficient openness to collaboration, and weak professional support among colleagues are still present in many institutions (Korać, 2020, pp. 65–67). In environments characterized by conflict, professional isolation, or lack of mutual trust, educators may experience demotivation and uncertainty in their professional development. In contrast, research indicates that a culture of horizontal learning, collegial exchange of experiences, and reflective dialogue represents an important factor in professional empowerment and the development of professional identity.

Despite numerous challenges, contemporary literature suggests that supportive professional communities, opportunities for reflective practice, and the development of professional autonomy are key factors in preserving professional integrity and improving the quality of educators' work. Therefore, increasing emphasis is placed on creating conditions that will enable the professional empowerment of educators, strengthening a collaborative culture, and reducing administrative and structural barriers in everyday practice.

Concluding Remarks

Despite the numerous challenges and difficulties of the the profession, mentioned above, there is also significant potential for positive influence and meaningful change. These opportunities

create a foundation for further strengthening and advancing the profession in both its status and practice.

One of the key prerequisites for improving the professional position of educators relates to the enhancement of working conditions in preschool institutions. Large group sizes, lack of space, insufficient material resources, and limited professional support significantly hinder the implementation of contemporary curricular approaches based on individualization, child participation, and reflective practice. In this regard, improving the quality of the preschool system is not possible without creating organizational and material conditions that enable educators to fulfill professional requirements in a high-quality manner.

Particular attention should also be directed toward reducing preschool teachers' administrative burden. Although documentation and evaluation represent an important part of contemporary professional practice, their excessive formalization often leads to administrative tasks overshadowing meaningful work with children. Future reform activities should therefore focus on simplifying procedures and developing functional forms of documentation that genuinely serve reflection and practice improvement, rather than primarily fulfilling formal system requirements.

An important step in strengthening the professional status of preschool teachers is also their greater involvement in decision-making processes related to preschool education. Practitioners should be active participants in the design and evaluation of educational policies, as they are the ones who directly implement reform processes in practice. Strengthening professional autonomy and valuing practitioners' experience can contribute to a greater sense of professional competence, responsibility, and belonging to the profession.

In addition to institutional changes, improving the social position of preschool teachers also requires a shift in the societal perception of the profession. It is necessary to more strongly affirm the importance of early childhood education for the development of the child and society as a whole, as well as the complexity and expertise of the early educator's professional role. Greater visibility of the profession in public discourse, continuous investment in professional development, and more adequate financial recognition of work could contribute to strengthening professional prestige and motivation for entering and remaining in the profession.

Finally, improving the professional status of preschool teachers presupposes the development of a culture of collaboration, support, and shared learning within institutions. A professional community based on mutual trust, reflection, and exchange of experiences represents an important foundation for professional development and the preservation of professional identity. Only in conditions where the profession is valued, supported, and recognized as a significant factor in social development can we speak of a genuine improvement in the position of early childhood educators in contemporary society.

References

- Akkerman, S. F., & Meijer, P. C. (2011). A dialogical approach to conceptualizing teacher identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 27*(2), 308–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2010.08.013>
- Androusou, A., & Tsafos, V. (2018). Aspects of the professional identity of preschool teachers in Greece: Investigating the role of teacher education and professional experience. *Teacher Development, 22*(4), 554–570. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2018.1438309>
- Banković, I. (2014). Early childhood professionalism in Serbia: current issues and developments. *International Journal of Early Years Education, 22*(3), 251–262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2014.944885>

- Beijaard, D., Meijer, P. C., & Verloop, N. (2004). Reconsidering research on teachers' professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(2), 107–128.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2003.07.001>
- Hanhikoski, E., & Sevón, E. (2024). Early childhood education and care teachers' narratives of their professional identity. *Journal of Early Childhood Education Research*, 13(2), 55-77.
<https://doi.org/10.58955/jecer.129076>
- Jurčević Lozančić, A. (2023). Radne orijentacije, smisao posla, profesionalni identitet i zadovoljstvo odgojitelja. *Nova prisutnost: časopis za intelektualna i duhovna pitanja*, 21(2), 285-299.
<https://doi.org/10.31192/np.21.2.3>
- Kizevski, M., & Radović, S. (2023). Vaspitački posao u Srbiji iz perspektive vaspitača. *Krugovi detinjstva – časopis za multidisciplinarna istraživanja detinjstva*, 11(2), 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.53406/kd.v11i2.81>
- Korać, I. (2020). *Horizontalno učenje u funkciji podsticanja profesionalnog razvoja nastavnika i vaspitača* [Doktorska disertacija, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu]. NARDUS.
https://nardus.mpn.gov.rs/handle/123456789/17969?locale-attribute=sr_RS
- Korać, I., & Đermanov, J. (2023). Horizontalno učenje: izazovi za promene u profesionalnom razvoju nastavnika i vaspitača. *DHS – Društvene i humanističke studije*, 2(23), 523–540.
<https://doi.org/10.51558/24903647.2023.8.2.523>
- Korthagen, F. A. J. (2004). In search of the essence of a good teacher: Towards a more holistic approach in teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(1), 77–97.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2003.10.002>
- Krnjaja, Ž. (2016). *Gde stanije kvalitet: Razvijanje prakse dečjeg vrtića*. Institut za pedagogiju i andragogiju Filozofskog fakulteta Univerziteta u Beogradu.
- Mihić, I. (2017). Doživljaj kompetentnosti i motivacija vaspitača za rad sa decom sa smetnjama u razvoju. *Godišnjak Filozofskog fakulteta u Novom Sadu*, 42(2), 339-359.
<https://doi.org/10.19090/gff.2017.2.339-359>
- Miljković, J. (2011). Ugled vaspitno-obrazovnih profesija. *Inovacije u nastavi*, 24(3), 42-52.
<https://reff.f.bg.ac.rs/bitstream/id/151/1156.pdf>
- Ministarstvo prosvete, nauke i tehnološkog razvoja Republike Srbije. (2018). *Pravilnik o osnovama programa predškolskog vaspitanja i obrazovanja („Godine uzleta“)*. Službeni glasnik Republike Srbije – Prosvetni glasnik, 16/2018.
http://demo.paragraf.rs/demo/combined/Old/t/t2018_09/t09_0093.htm
- Pavlović-Breneselović, D., & Krnjaja, Ž. (2012). Perspektiva vaspitača o profesionalnom usavršavanju sa stanovišta sistemske koncepcije profesionalnog razvoja. *Andragoške studije*, 1, 145-161.
https://as.edu.rs/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/AS_2012-1_09.pdf
- Salamon, A., Sumsion, J., Press, F., & Harrison, L. (2016). Implicit theories and naïve beliefs: Using the theory of practice architectures to deconstruct the practices of early childhood educators. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 14(4), 431–443. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X14563857>
- Stamenković, I. (2025). Ciljevi i vrednosti u koncipiranju i realizaciji programa inicijalnog obrazovanja vaspitača. *Pedagoška stvarnost*, 71(2), 192–207.
<https://pedagoskastvarnost.ff.uns.ac.rs/index.php/ps/article/view/281/166>
- Stanković, Lj. P., Vuletić, S. D., & Jovanović, M. Ž. (2019). Razvoj profesionalnih kompetencija studenata vaspitača: Metodološke kompetencije. *Pedagoška stvarnost*, 65(2), 67–82.
<https://pefja.kg.ac.rs/pctja-19-67s/>
- Trede, F., Macklin, R., & Bridges, D. (2012). Professional identity development: A review of the higher education literature. *Studies in Higher Education*, 37(3), 365–384.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2010.521237>
- Zakon o visokom obrazovanju [Law on Higher Education]. (2025). Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, Nos. 88/2017, 73/2018, 27/2018 – another law, 67/2019, 6/2020 – another law, 11/2021 – authentic interpretation, 67/2021, 67/2021 - another law, 76/2023 and 19/
https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_visokom_obrazovanju.html

PROFESIONALNI IDENTITET VASPITAČA U SAVREMENOM DRUŠTVU: IZMEĐU OČEKIVANJA I REALNOSTI

Katarina Tomić

Akademija vaspitačko medicinskih strukovnih studija Kruševac

Apstrakt

Savremeno društvo postavlja pred vaspitače sve kompleksnije zahteve, koji prevazilaze tradicionalne okvire njihove profesionalne uloge. Od njih se očekuje da budu istovremeno pedagozi, psiholozi, inovatori, digitalno kompetentni stručnjaci i saradnici u zajednici. U tom kontekstu, profesionalni identitet vaspitača oblikuje se na preseku institucionalnih očekivanja, društvenih normi i ličnih vrednosti, često stvarajući tenziju između idealizovanih uloga i realnih uslova rada. Cilj ovog rada je da analizira ključne dimenzije profesionalnog identiteta vaspitača u savremenom obrazovnom sistemu, sa posebnim osvrtom na izazove koji proizlaze iz ubrzanih društvenih promena, digitalizacije i promenjenih očekivanja roditelja i institucija. Rad se oslanja na savremene teorijske pristupe profesionalnom identitetu, kao i na empirijska saznanja o percepciji uloge vaspitača. Posebna pažnja posvećena je diskrepanci između normativnog okvira profesije i svakodnevne prakse, kao i strategijama koje vaspitači razvijaju kako bi očuvali profesionalnu autonomiju i integritet. U radu se razmatra i značaj kontinuiranog profesionalnog razvoja, refleksivne prakse i podrške sistema u izgradnji stabilnog i koherentnog profesionalnog identiteta. Zaključno, ukazuje se na potrebu redefinisivanja društvenih i institucionalnih očekivanja, kako bi se profesionalni identitet vaspitača uskladio sa realnim mogućnostima i potrebama savremenog obrazovanja, čime bi se unapredio kvalitet vaspitno-obrazovnog rada i položaj vaspitača u društvu.

Ključne reči: profesionalni identitet, vaspitači, savremeno društvo, profesionalni razvoj, refleksivna praksa